

Appendix: Methodological toolbox

Tool no. 3_4_3_7	
Title	<i>Fritidsfiskeappen</i>
Category	Socio-cultural, Ecological (<i>for Ghostfishing</i>)
Purpose of the method	<i>This is an app by the Directorate of Fisheries. Users can report on the exact location and type of equipment that they have lost in the sea. If the lost gear has been removed from the seabed, the removal can be reported as well. The data for these reports is visualized and accessible for previous years as well. We will use it to monitor the amount of reports.</i>
Effort in time	<i>The app exists already. Retrieving the information from it, will require minimum amount of time.</i>
Number of objects investigated	<i>N/A.</i>
Data format	<i>numerical</i>
Description	<i>The app allows users to report their lost gear and for under-water cleaners to report when they have removed gear from the seabed. It is visualized in a map but also in tables and other numerical and textual formats. It is created and run by the Directorate of Fisheries and accessible by the public.</i>
Basic Literature	<i>Fritidsfiskeappen. Fiskeridirektoratet. https://www.fiskeridir.no/Fritidsfiske/Meld-tapt-og-funnen-reiskap</i>
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Linked material	